

XORIJY TILLARNI O'QITISHDA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLAR NAZARIYANING AMALIYOTGA TATBIQI

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MODERN METHODS IN TEACHING KOREAN AND THEIR EFFECTIVENESS

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Abstract. *This scientific article provides information about modern methods for teaching Korean, which are currently useful and comprehensive. In addition, the concepts of method, methodology, and methodology are explained, and their characteristics are highlighted.*

Keywords: *method, methodology, Korean language, comparative method, correct method, history, mixed.*

Introduction

In the era of globalization, learning multiple languages has become increasingly important worldwide. Learning a language not only allows you to speak the language of a country, but also contributes greatly to understanding its culture, economy, and history. Today, the demand for learning Korean has increased significantly due to the influence of Korean culture. Although traditional teaching methods are the basis, they are evolving to incorporate innovative technologies and methodologies to meet the needs of 21st century learners.

Method (Greek: "methodos" - a way of knowing or research, theory, doctrine) is a specific method or path used to achieve a certain goal. It is a tool used to solve a problem or achieve a result. Many general and specific scientific methods are used in modern science. Especially in the last century, new forms of modeling and mathematical methods have developed, cybernetic modeling and computer modeling methods are widely used in almost all areas of society. Modern scientific methods help researchers uncover the secrets of the world. Methodology is a system of methods and rules used to effectively implement a certain activity or process. It determines what methods should be used to achieve a goal and in what order they should be performed. It explains the general laws of the educational process and shows ways to apply them in practice, and is aimed at forming the knowledge, skills and competencies of students. Includes teaching methods, tools, technologies, and assessment systems.

Methodology is the science of methods, that is, a system that studies which methods should be used in the process of research and activity, their effectiveness and

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scientific basis. Methodology studies and analyzes methods, determines which method works best in which conditions. It determines the criteria for choosing methods, helps in choosing methods that are suitable for research or process. It has a theoretical and practical basis - it explains not only practical methods, but also their scientific basis.

If we look at the history of teaching a foreign language, historically, methods have been divided into four groups. These are: translation, direct, comparative and mixed methods. **Translation method** – This method is based on the Grammar Translation Method, in which words and sentences in a foreign language are translated into the native language. It mainly helps to translate foreign language texts word for word or literally, to understand the language through grammatical rules and translation, and to master the language through reading and translating texts. **Direct method** – This method focuses on explaining and communicating directly in the foreign language without translating it into the native language. In this case, learners mainly use only the language being studied, and the language is taught through pictures, actions and sound examples. **Comparative method** – Its full name is “conscious-comparative method”. The founder of this method was Acad.L. V. Shcherba adapted the method to the modern process of teaching a foreign language. This method is based on comparing the similarities and differences between the language being studied and the native language of the learner. **Mixed method** - the mixed method arose as a mixture of the principles of the direct and comparative methods. It is mainly aimed at the combined use of grammar and translation methods, the direct method and the comparative approach, the combined use of online resources and textbooks, and the study of the language from a theoretical and practical perspective. Thus, all the methods in the centuries-old history of teaching a foreign language are grouped into the four categories above. It is necessary to briefly analyze each of them, since some of their features are used in a specific form in today's methodology. Now we will consider and analyze modern methods that are currently widely used in teaching foreign languages, especially in teaching Korean.

Gamification is the application of game elements to other types of social activities. This movement aims to engage and motivate participants to achieve desired goals. The main thing is that games are dynamic and versatile. They are used in various fields, with endless applications for various purposes. Examples of these are applications such as Duolingo, Memrise and Babbel. Its effectiveness lies in making learning interesting, increasing motivation and promoting consistent practice.

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Blended learning combines traditional classroom methods with online resources. In this, students learn theory online, i.e. from videos, e-books and practice in person. Its important aspect is that it maintains human interaction and provides flexibility for speaking and listening skills. This method is one of the methods that I have historically highlighted above. **Task-Based Learning (TBLT)** - lessons are focused on performing practical tasks, such as ordering food at a restaurant, writing a blog post or translating a short text. This method develops real-world communication skills and builds students' confidence. TBL encourages learners to actively use the target language while simultaneously developing their problem-solving, critical thinking, and decision-making skills. **Use of media and cultural content** – Incorporating K-pop songs, K-drama scripts, and Korean films into lessons makes learning fun and culturally relevant. In this way, students not only gain language proficiency, but also cultural fluency, strengthening a deeper connection with the language. **AI and adaptive learning** – Artificial intelligence personalizes learning by adapting content based on the progress and needs of the learner. For example, AI tutors like ChatGPT or Lingvist platforms. The effectiveness is that they adapt lessons to individual strengths and weaknesses. **Social learning** – Learning through social interaction with native speakers or peers. Learning through language exchange platforms, group discussions, forums, or study groups. The effectiveness is to improve conversational skills and build confidence. **Flipped Classroom Method** – Students learn the basics at home through videos or readings and focus on practice and discussion during class. The effectiveness is to maximize interactive, hands-on activities in the classroom. **Inquiry-Based Learning** – Encourages students to ask questions, research, and find answers independently. Instead of direct explanations, teachers set problems for students to learn and solve. **Competency-Based Learning** – Students develop based on their ability to demonstrate their skills, rather than spending a certain amount of time on a subject. For example, instead of moving through the curriculum at the same pace, students advance as they prove their understanding. **Socratic Method** – Teaches through questioning, critical thinking, and dialogue. The teacher asks thought-provoking questions to encourage deep thinking instead of giving direct answers.

Conclusion

Learning a foreign language is a multifaceted learning process, in which a person undergoes complex psychological changes. In particular, a process of comparing a foreign language with a native language occurs. Various teaching

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methods and technologies are used in this process. Using modern pedagogical technologies, teaching a foreign language with a native language gives effective results. Modern language learning methods prioritize presence, activity, and practical skills. They make it easier than ever to effectively learn a new language, offering different approaches to achieving different learning styles and goals. Combining these methods with consistent effort and motivation can lead to significant success in language acquisition. Modern teaching methods are aimed at developing critical thinking, creativity, collaboration, and digital literacy. They are aimed at student activity, problem-solving, and real-life application rather than passive memorization. The key to successful modern education is a balance between technology, active learning, and student-centered approaches.

List of used literature:

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